

A Mini-Review on The Role of Telemedicine in the Management of Parkinson's Disease

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Abstract

Background: Parkinson's disease (PD) is a progressive neurological disorder that usually affects the older age group. Neurologists across the globe are limited especially in rural areas with no access to health facilities. Telemedicine has however, been an effective tool in ensuring that health care is accessible to all, irrespective of geographical location and socioeconomic status.

Telemedicine has shown to improve not just the health care system but also patients' well-being and satisfaction. Although, telemedicine has its shortcomings that limits its widespread use such as medical license laws in some part of the world, poor network connectivity in rural areas, poor electrical supply and computer illiteracy in aged people, there are strategies that can be put in place to eliminate the aforementioned.

Conclusion: The future of telemedicine in the management of PD is extremely encouraging but more research needs to be done in order to understand the challenges and limitations and further improve areas that needs adjustments.

Keywords: telemedicine, telehealth, tele-treatment, teleconsultation, telemonitoring

1. Introduction

Neurological disorders are one of the major causes of disability and death all over the world leading to an increase in demand for neurological specialists, despite this, a significant lack of neurological specialists in some part of the world has been reported to play a role in the cause of death. In order to lessen these increasing numbers of disability and death while also providing more resources in terms of training specialists and making equipment available, the role of telehealth in the management of neurological diseases particularly movement disorders such as Parkinson's disease cannot be overemphasized [4].

Parkinson's disease is the 2nd most common neurodegenerative brain disease, a slowly progressive disease that is common in older age groups but can occur at any age [1]. The disease has four major motor symptoms which includes, tremor, rigidity, akinesia or bradykinesia and postural rigidity (TRAP). Other motor and non-motor symptoms occur but these four motor symptoms are pathognomonic of Parkinson's disease that should not be missed [1].

Telemedicine is usually done in real time by making use of a video conference call which involves the managing doctor and the patient. It is the long-distance relationship of medicine that happens between patients and their doctors. This might not be ideal, however because of the peculiarity of Parkinson's disease, which can be diagnosed based on clinical observation by a trained neurology, this allows for patients previously without a chance, to see a neurologist especially in rural areas and in turn saves time in places with neurologist but limited access to physically see one because of one reason or the other. All this, improves healthcare in the long run both in rural and urban areas [1,2]. Shortcomings in relation to teleconsultations are possible, however, it should not be totally erased as the benefit outweighs the risks and also depends on individuality [2].

Although, before the COVID 19 was declared a pandemic in 2020, telehealth was used in the management of movement disorders. However, telemedicine has proven to have helped out during the COVID 19 pandemic when all the focus was on combating the viral disease, in the hope of not contracting the disease when trying to get basic treatment for Parkinson's, priority was given to telemedicine and there was improvement in access to health care and patients satisfaction on follow up cases. This doesn't negate the fact that physical contact for general and neurological examinations is more suitable and preferable for first time patients, however emphasis should be made on the usefulness of telemedicine in places without neurological specialists [1,2].

Telemedicine comprises of three major parts that includes; tele-consultation, tele-monitoring and tele-treatment. While teleconsultation can be used interchangeably with telemedicine, telemonitoring makes use of tools such as body sensors and specific applications using mobile devices that can be used to gather information about patients useful for both health care workers and researchers [2]. It is no doubt that effective and consistent use of telemedicine in PD will significantly improve global health especially due to the fact that telehealth is easy to use, effective and widely available to some extent [3].

Telemedicine has shown to be effective with little drawbacks in terms of neurological examinations and this is due to the fact that a greater part of neurological examinations can be visualized and others that need to be elicited on patients can be explained, step-by-step to the caregivers or other health related personnel [4].

2. Advantages of Telemedicine in The Management of Parkinson's Disease

Telemedicine has been great since the era of COVID 19 pandemic, it has prevented many patients with PD from contracting the disease while in search of basic treatment or follow up [2].

It has improved access to neurological specialists in places that do not have a standard health-care and places with shortage of manpower, it is cost effective, time-saving and delivers access to a trained specialist at any given time [1,2]. Another advantage that telehealth provide, is the satisfaction that it gives to patients as treatment is usually home based at the comfort of their homes, this reduces stress and in fact, prevents additional stress to patients such as eradication of unnecessary waiting-time or long-distance travels [2,3]. Interestingly, telemedicine in form of tele-education is also very useful in the enrollment and training of physicians in places that lack capacity for physical training. Distance learning conducted by international bodies for rural areas can significantly improve health care in the long run [4]. Patients who are bedridden and unable to travel long distances for follow up cases can benefit significantly from telemedicine [5]. Recently, in Nigeria, telemedicine has been shown to expose fake drugs that are being circulated to the general public with potentially harmful substances which can even lead to loss of life or vital organs. Mobile devices are used to alert the Nigerian Agency of Food and Drug Administration Control (NAFDAC) via Text Messages [7]. For undeveloped places, with no infrastructure or limited access to health care and internet, tele prescription can be used to manage simple ailments, this will in turn reduce the cost of transportation that is due to traveling long distances and reduce self-medication and even quackery practices which is potentially harmful [7].

3. Barriers and Limitations in Accessing Telemedicine services.

Although, the advantages of telemedicine have been well acknowledged by both neurologists and patients and has improved the health care system by bringing equity and access to health care especially in places that used to lack, some studies have shown that telemedicine still has its flaws and some specific concerns are lack of physical examination.

3.2. Nonavailability of what is needed to aid telemedicine services

The priority of most Africa countries is how to build their economy, in the process of trying to do so, health care is often neglected. [6,7}. For telemedicine to work, it needs a substantial amount of electrical supply which is lacking in most parts of Africa, especially in rural areas where it is needed the most [7,8]. Another factor that is also very important as a cause of low turn-out of telemedicine is poor network and even the lack of funds by low-income earners to get data supply [8]. Other factors include, the unavailability of infrastructures and poor communication. In places where telemedicine is needed, like in rural areas, most people have zero computer literacy and others have never even used a mobile phone before, let alone checked up things on the internet [8].

3.3. Confidentiality

Confidentiality and privacy are very sensitive areas in medical practice and if care is not taken, patients might be stigmatized by even health care workers unknowingly [4]. Telemedicine has to do with receiving patient data and saving it or transferring it to a device that would be used for consultation or management [9]. In some cases, the communication devices are not controlled by the patient which could lead to serious breach in data privacy that might stigmatize the patient [8].

3.4. Legal Concerns

State licensing regulations cause a huge barrier in providing health-care both for patients and health professionals and these regulations are put in place due to long distances and even different geographical locations. [6]. The issue of practicing license is a big issue in most parts of the world as it is said that physicians that do not train in specific countries

can also not practice there. Another issue at hand, is the case of the rights of a referring doctor to reject or accept second opinions from a doctor consulted, as a referring doctor is the one in charge of the patients [6-8].

Strategies for promoting Telemedicine services.

- I. Implement of data security must be done such as encryption of data and using only applications that are secured and informed consent should be taken and education should be given especially in cases where mobile devices are not handled by patients in case of computer illiteracy.
- II. There should be a legal framework drafted by governments. Guidelines, and the repercussions of not following them should be clearly stated.
- III. Patients that are not conversant with the use of computer gadgets should be trained, so also, physicians in order to have clear communications between both parties.
- IV. Governments should prioritize building and contributing to the health-care system in order to eliminate minor setbacks such as poor network connectivity and unavailability of electricity.

4. Methodology

This is short review was conducted by examining recent literature on the use of telemedicine in the management of Parkinson's disease. A narrative approach was used.

Search Strategy

The following databases were searched;

- Scopus
- Pubmed
- Google scholar

- Cochrane Library

The search covered studies from 2015 to 2023 to include a decade of recent evidences on telemedicine and Parkinson's disease.

Inclusion and Exclusion criteria

Inclusion:

- Articles published in English
- Peer-reviewed original studies, systemic reviews, and meta analyses.
- Studies analysing telemedicine interventions for the diagnosis and management of Parkinson's disease.

Exclusion

- Studies unrelated to telemedicine
- Studies not related to parkinson's disease

Ethical Considerations: Not applicable

5. Conclusion

Despite some flaws associated with tele-neurology, it is still an effective tool in the management of Parkinson's Disease and other movement disorders especially in places lacking neurologists and places with little man power, places like rural areas, to be more specific. This review was determined to confirm the effectiveness of telemedicine in the management of Parkinson's disease. From this study, obviously, telemedicine has placed a huge role in health care, it has in fact, done better than harm. Rural areas now have access to neurologists, travel costs have been saved and diverted to medication funds, overall, patients have gotten better. However, there are still areas that needs improvement such as, places with poor internet access, places with medical license laws, etc.

In conclusion, this review supported the use of telemedicine in the management of Parkinson's disease, but the quality of research could improve significantly in order to shed more light on the advantages and disadvantages of telemedicine in the management of Parkinson's disease.

List of Abbreviations

PD: Parkinson's Disease

COVID-19: Corona Virus Disease of 2019

Declarations

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References

1. Current perspectives on the role of telemedicine in the management of Parkinson's disease Open Access Full Text Article. Joel L Eisenberg, Jyhong Gabriel Hou, Peter J Barbour, Department of Neurology, Lehigh Valley Health Network, Allentown, PA, USA; Morsani College of Medicine, University of South Florida, Tampa, FL USA.
2. Van den Bergh R, Bloem BR, Meinders MJ, Evers LJW. The state of telemedicine for persons with Parkinson's disease. *Curr Opin Neurol*. 2021 Aug 1;34(4):589-597. doi: 10.1097/WCO.0000000000000953. PMID: 33990100; PMCID: PMC8279892.
3. Desirèe Latella, Giuseppa Maresca, Caterina Formica, Chiara Sorbera, Amelia Bringandì, Giuseppe Di Lorenzo, Angelo Quartarone and Silvia Marino. The Role of Telemedicine

in the Treatment of Cognitive and Psychological Disorders in Parkinson's Disease: An Overview. *Brain Sci.* 2023, 13(3), 499; <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci13030499>

4. Cubo E, Delgado-López PD. Telemedicine in the Management of Parkinson's Disease: Achievements, Challenges, and Future Perspectives. *Brain Sci.* 2022Dec 19;12(12):1735. doi: 10.3390/brainsci12121735. PMID: 36552194; PMCID: PMC9775481.
5. Wechsler LR. Advantages and limitations of teleneurology. *JAMA Neurol.* 2015Mar;72(3):349-54. doi: 10.1001/jamaneurol.2014.3844. PMID: 25580942.
6. Expanding Access to Specialized Care Through Telemedicine for Parkinson's Disease. Penn Medicine, Philadelphia, PA 800-789-7366. July 19, 2023
7. Okoroafor IJ, Chukwunke FN, Ifebunandu N, Onyeka TC, Ekwueme CO, Agwuna KK. Telemedicine and biomedical care in Africa: Prospects and challenges. *Niger J Clin Pract* 2017;20:1-5.
8. Maurice Mars, School of Medicine, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Congella, South Africa. Telemedicine and Advances in Urban and Rural Healthcare Delivery in Africa Nelson R. Mandela
9. Dr.A.Shaji George¹, A.S.Hovan George.T elemedicine: A New Way to Provide Healthcare. *Partners Universal International Innovation Journal (PUIIJ)* Volume: 01 Issue: 03 | May-June 2023 | www.puiij.com